

Repeated Impact Behavior of Woven Composites in Arctic Conditions

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Keywords: Dynamic Impact; Arctic Exposure; Damage; Delamination; Computational Modeling

1. Introduction

Recent rise in demand and interest in arctic exploration calls for the understanding of mechanical behavioral aspects of naval structures in extreme conditions. Naval materials typically experience drastic changes and degradation in their macro-and-microstructures when exposed to sea water and cold temperatures. Hence, it is critical to focus on the damage and types of failure that occur during service after exposed to extreme conditions, and develop methods for improving the damage resistance, tolerance, and life cycle of the naval materials being used. Sandwich composites are preferred for naval hull structures due to their lightweight, enhanced performance and affordability. A sandwich composite consists of two thin, but stiff face sheets bonded with a lightweight and damping core between them. Commonly used materials for sandwich face sheets are carbon and glass fiber composites, while aluminum and a variety of foams are utilized for sandwich cores. Naval applications expose these types of materials to adverse environments like sea water, wave impact, low and high temperatures, etc. with time resulting in surface alterations, internal damage, and degradation of their chemical and mechanical properties, ultimately compromising the safety of the naval structure. Face sheet composites in marine applications are typically subjected to repeated impact of waves [1]. There have been several studies on the response of composites under repeated impact at room temperature. Rajkumar et al. [2] studied the effect of repeated low-velocity impacts on the tensile strength of fiber metal laminates and found that the peak load, impact energy, and failure strain decreased with increasing number of impacts. Morais et al. [3] investigated the effect of repeated low energy impact response on carbon-epoxy composites with different stacking sequences, and reported that cross-ply and non-symmetric laminates have a better endurance against low impact than unidirectional laminates.

Many researchers have reported that low and high temperatures change the response of composite materials. Several studies have been performed to understand the effect of temperature on the impact response of composites. Icten et al. [4] studied the impact behavior of laminated glass-epoxy composites at 20 C, -20 C and -60 C with energies varying from 5 J to 70 J, and established that the dominant damage modes for energies below 20 J were matrix cracking and delamination, and that for energies above 20 J was fiber breakage. Bienias et al. [5] investigated the influence of repeated low velocity and low energy impacts on carbon and glass fiber composites, and stated that carbon fibers have lower resistance to repeated impact than laminates with glass fibers. Gomez-del Rio [6] investigated the response of CFRPs at low impact velocities and temperatures ranging from 20 C to -150 C, and found that decrease in temperature caused higher damage to the laminate. Badawy et al. [7] investigated the impact behavior of GFRP exposed to temperatures in the range of -10 C, 20 C, 50 C and 80 C, showed that the damage area increased with decrease in temperature. Erickson et al. investigated the effect of temperature on the absorbed energy, maximum impact force and damage mechanisms in sandwich composite panels at -25 C, 25 C and 75 C, and found similar effects of temperature. Icten et al. [8] examined the response of woven glass-epoxy composites subjected to single and repeated impact at room temperature and -50 C, and found that the temperature is extremely important for determining the response of the composite to single and repeated impact. There have been several studies on single impact at room and at low temperatures; however, seldom work has been reported on repeated impact at low temperatures. In this study, repeated impact of woven carbon composite face sheets was investigated at room temperature and arctic temperature (-50 C).

The focus of this paper was on exploring the influence of arctic temperatures (-60 °C to -50 °C) on the dynamic impact (single and repeated) behavior on carbon woven/vinyl ester composites. In particular, dynamic impact behavior under dry and arctic conditioned (-50 °C) were investigated next at energies in the range of 2 J to 35 J. Determining the degree of damage and exploring the types of failure modes under varying conditions are the main focus of this paper.

2. Manufacturing

Laminates of 16 layers were manufactured according to the ASTM Standard D7136/D7136M in a 12 by 12 in. aluminum mold by the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process [9]. Laminates were fabricated by placing layers of woven carbon fiber in an aluminum mold with flow media, breather and nylon ply, as it can be seen in **Figure 1**. This was followed by enclosing the mold in a vacuum bag and drawing it into vacuum in order to aid infiltration of the resin (vinyl ester resin). The specimens for arctic and room temperatures were manufactured together as one laminate in order to ensure that the curing conditions were identical as it can be seen in **Figure 2**. A total of 6 laminates were manufactured. From each laminate 6 samples were obtained (3 for room temperature and 3 for arctic temperature).

Figure 1: VARTM configuration for the laminate

Figure 2: Manufactured laminate dimensions

3. Arctic Exposure and In-Situ Dynamic Impact Tests

Carbon woven laminates were manufactured and tested at 25 °C and -50 °C. The low-energy impact tests were performed at room temperature in a CEAAT 9340 impact machine. From each test, time, load, energy, velocity and deflection were obtained. Drop-weight impact tests were performed using a CEAAT 9340 Drop Tower Impact System on rectangular laminate specimens of 6.0 in. (152.4 mm) length x 4.0 in. (100 mm) width and thicknesses of 4.02 ± 0.13 mm for tests at 25°C and -50°C, respectively. The laminates were clamped by a pneumatic fixture mounted with a test area of 7.07 in² (45.6 cm²) inside an environmental chamber (thermostatic controller from -50 °C to 150 °C). The impact loading applied using a hemispherical impactor (striker) with a mass of 5.05 kg and diameter of 0.5 in. (12.7 mm) was concentrated at the center of the specimen in the out-of-plane direction as shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Impact testing set up

Five samples each were impacted with energies of 2, 10, 20, 25, 30, and 35 Joules at room and arctic temperatures. The corresponding force-time, energy-time and force-displacement plots were obtained for each test. The samples used for arctic conditions were placed in a freezer at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a period of 90 days to obtain a uniform temperature distribution in the specimen, and were then tested in an environmental chamber that was conditioned with LN_2 for 15 min. at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ prior to impact loading.

4. Results and Discussion

Typical energy-time and force-displacement plots are shown in **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**. The slope of the force-deflection curve represents the impact-bending stiffness, which appears to decrease with increasing number of impacts. The load-time graph for the repeated impact has 4 phases of force change: stabilization, force increase, time of reaching the maximum force and force decrease stage [5]. **Figure 6** represents the load-time response of a sample impacted at 20 J at room temperature. The first impact represents the stabilization phase. In this stage, the peak force is the result of the compaction of the thin and unreinforced matrix layer, which hardens the laminate. The second stage is force increased. This stage is represented by the second impact in which the impacted force increased due to the hardened surface of the laminate. At this stage, there is still compaction of the matrix. The third stage is reaching the maximum force, which is at the fifth impact. Before the fifth impact, there was no visible damage to the laminate, only small indentation. This can be seen in the slope of Fig.~\ref{20J} in which the slope remains almost constant with no significant change. Finally, the fourth stage is represented by the sixth impact in which the impacted force decreased. After this impact, there was a significant decrease in slope and damage such as fiber breakage. This behavior was presented only for the samples impacted at 20 J at room and arctic temperature.

Figure 4: Energy-time response at 25J

Figure 5: Force-displacement response at 25 J

Figure 6: Normalized force-time graph response at 20 J

Absorbed energy as a function of temperature

The trends of absorbed energy vs. temperature are different at different impact energy levels. The absorbed energy is higher as the impact energy increases. For the samples impacted with the same energies, the absorbed energies were lower when impacted at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in comparison to the room temperature tests. Figure 3 shows the impacted surface and back surface after the first impact of samples impacted at 20 J and 35 J at room and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature. For 20 J, there is no visible damage on the laminate; however, the sample absorbed energy as seen in Figure 4. This absorption is the result of internal matrix cracks and delamination. Samples impacted at 25 J, 30 J and 35 J showed visible damage such as fiber fracture on the back face of the impacted laminate. At $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the laminates were rigid and absorbed less energy than the samples impacted at room temperature as shown in **Figure 7**. The main factor contributing to energy absorption was matrix cracks.

Figure 7: Impacted samples at room temperature and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Repeated impacts tests showed that the degree of damage for an impact energy increased with the number of impacts. **Figure 8** shows the plots of absorbed energy and degree of damage vs. number of impacts. It is observed that the specimens absorb more energy every time they were hit by the striker. As the impact energy increased less impacts were required to perforate the laminate. When the impacted energy was less than 20 J, the degree of damage remains constant. However, for impact energies of 20 J and 25 J, the degree of damage remains almost constant during the earlier impacts and then increases almost linearly. For 30 J and 35 J, the degree of damage increased linearly.

Figure 8: (a) Absorbed energy versus the number of impacts; Degree of damage versus number of impact

Deflection as a function of temperature

The deflection of the specimens depend on the temperature as shown in **Figure 9**. In all cases, deflection at room temperature was higher than at arctic temperatures. At $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the laminates behaved in a rigid

manner with very small deflections. While the samples impacted at room temperature showed higher deflections. The mechanism mainly responsible for deflection of the samples at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was striker penetration, while bending dominated at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 9: Deflection versus the number of impacts at room temperature and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Impact force as a function of temperature

The impact force of the laminates at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ were higher than the ones tested at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ as seen in **Figure 10**. This is attributed to the rigidity of the laminate at low temperatures. As mentioned previously, the maximum impact force is reached at the third impact for 20 J samples. For the 25 J, 30 J and 35 J, the maximum force was obtained at the first impact. For these cases, fiber fracture was the dominant failure mode, while for 20 J it was a combination of matrix cracks and delamination.

Figure 10: Impact force versus the number of impacts at room temperature and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Impact-induced damage pictures of impacted laminates at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 J and 35 J are shown in **Figure 11**. For the same impact energies, the damage area of the laminate impacted at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ increased and was more prominent. For 20 J and 25 J, more impacts were needed to perforate the laminate at arctic temperatures. For 30 J and 35 J, the number of impacts required to perforate the laminates at room and arctic temperatures were comparable.

Figure 11: Impact force versus the number of impacts at room temperature and $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

5. Conclusion

The objective of this paper was to determine the impact and repeated impact behavior of woven carbon fiber/vinyl-ester matrix system at room and arctic temperatures. A total of 32 samples were tested for low-velocity impact, 16 samples at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 16 samples at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It was observed that in a repeated impact event, the specimens could experience up to 4 different stages in response: force stabilization, force increase, maximum force and force decrease. If the impact energy was high enough to cause a decrease on the stiffness during the first impact, the samples will only experience maximum force and force decrease mechanisms subsequently. However, if the impact does not cause significant damage during the first impact, the specimens will experience all four stages mentioned above. Temperature also affects the laminate response during a repeated impact event. Under arctic conditions, the laminates were more rigid and required more number of impacts for perforation as compared to the samples at room temperature. For this reason, these samples experienced an increase in the damage area and impact force in comparison to the samples at room temperature. The specimens tested at room temperature absorbed more energy and had higher deflections in comparison to the samples at $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The degree of damage was lower for the samples at arctic temperatures, which means that they absorbed less energy. As a result, arctic temperatures have an effect on the low-velocity response of laminated composites by making them more rigid. The next effort in this direction is to develop a computational modeling framework that is able to predict the extent of damage during repeated impact under arctic conditions.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to acknowledge the support through the DoD HBCU/MI Basic Research Grant (W911NF-15-1-0430) to conduct the research presented in this paper.

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